

VARIOUS TREATMENT METHODS FOR VARICOSE AND SPIDER VEINS

Mainly, varicose veins and spider veins are being treated by surgeries but you can also do some home treatments and therapies to prevent the risk of vein disease.

Home Treatments

Due to irregular blood flow in the legs, varicose veins and spider veins occur. To reduce the risk factor you can do these exercises at home:

Do not stand or sit for longer periods- According to a **vein doctor**, you should take a break after every 30 minutes if you have to stand or sit at work for a longer period. This will help your legs in moving blood back to the heart and will make good blood circulation in your legs. This results in the strengthening of your leg muscles.

Lose weight- If you are obese or overweight then a [vein specialist](#) will suggest you lose some weight. Because extra weight will put pressure on your legs that results in the blocking of vein valves. This will help you prevent varicose veins and spider veins from forming in the future.

Regular physical exercise- Doing regular exercise will add benefit to **vein treatment**. You need to do exercises in which leg involvement is more like walking, running, leg raise, ankle movement, etc. This will help to push blood back to the heart against gravity. This kind of exercise will make your legs and ankles strong.

Put your feet up when sitting, you have to rest your legs on a stool as much as possible. This will help the legs maintaining good blood circulation.

Wear compression stockings- This will grip your legs tightly that results in putting pressure on your legs. It will help in increasing the blood flow in the legs.

Non-Surgical Treatments

vein specialist li will give you some medicines to treat your varicose and spider vein symptoms like itching, swelling, and pain. These are some non-surgical treatments for varicose and spider veins.

Endovenous therapy- This procedure is also known as “Endovenous Laser Ablation” and “Radiofrequency Ablation”. Larger bulging surface veins of the legs are being treated in this procedure. A **vein doctor li** inserts a small tube in the vein in this process and places a small probe through the tube. At the tip of the probe, the device heats up and then closes the vein. This device uses a laser to seal the vein permanently. The normal flow of blood is being taken by the healthy veins around the sealed veins.

Sclerotherapy- For smaller varicose veins and spider veins the most common treatment is sclerotherapy. A chemical is being injected into the veins during **vein treatments**. This chemical causes valves to stick together, swell and seal shut. This results in the stopping of blood due to which veins turn into scar tissues. The vein should fade in a few weeks. Multiple **varicose vein treatments** needed for it to work again.

Closure system- The veins presented just beneath the skin is being treated by this procedure. The veins that are deeper could not be treated by this option. A kind of adhesive is used to close the veins permanently. At [vein treatment long island](#), you can also go for this procedure.